

Receptor-mediated transcytosis of nanobodies targeting the heparin-binding EGF-like growth factor in human blood-brain barrier models[☆]

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ABSTRACT

Transport of molecules into the brain is regulated by the blood-brain barrier (BBB). Receptor-mediated transcytosis (RMT) is a targeted vesicular transport mechanism of brain endothelial cells that can be employed to specifically transport large therapeutic molecules into the brain. ProHB-EGF is the transmembrane precursor of the heparin-binding EGF-like growth factor (HB-EGF) present on the intraluminal side of the brain endothelial cells. This molecule is characterized as an internalizing transport receptor with so far no discovery of endogenous ligands. In this study, we describe the selection and characterization of two nanobodies (named F12 and H7) with high binding affinity for proHB-EGF and their BBB transcytosis potential were tested *in vitro*. For the human BBB model, we found that a polarized co-culture environment was crucial for the expression and cell surface display of proHB-EGF. The ability of F12 and H7 to pass the BBB *via* RMT was demonstrated in both a primary human brain microvascular endothelial cell-based BBB model and a human induced pluripotent stem cell (hiPSC)-derived iBBB model. Our studies demonstrate that the proHB-EGF targeting Nbs are promising BBB shuttle molecules for delivery of therapeutic molecules into the brain.

1. Introduction

The Blood-brain barrier (BBB) maintains brain homeostasis *via* a highly integrated multi-cellular structure and strictly selective transport mechanisms [1,2]. As BBB unbiasedly keeps most molecules out of the brain, it also represents a challenge for efficient drug delivery into the brain. One strategy to selectively transport drugs across the BBB is to harness the receptor-mediated transcytosis (RMT) mechanism. RMT is a highly selective vesicular transport mechanism of brain endothelial cells which facilitates transport of large cargos such as peptides, proteins and nanoparticles across the BBB [3,4]. RMT is initiated by ligands binding to their designated receptors expressed on the apical side of polarized

brain endothelial cells, followed by the transport of the ligand-receptor complexes in vesicles through the cells, ending with dissociation of the bound ligands at the basolateral side of the endothelial cells and subsequent trafficking into the brain parenchyma [4]. Hence, a therapeutic molecule conjugated to such a ligand can be delivered into the brain in a targeted manner. To date, several RMT-enabled receptors on the BBB have been explored for cerebral drug delivery, such as transferrin receptor (TfR), insulin receptor (InsR) and low-density lipoprotein receptor (LDLR) [5,6]. Notwithstanding, these approaches share therapeutic limitations due to binding competition from endogenous ligands. This results in low drug delivery efficiency, or impediment of necessary cerebral nutrients transport, which leads to metabolic dysfunctions or

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cytotoxicity [7,8].

ProHB-EGF is the membrane-bound precursor of heparin-binding EGF-like growth factor (HB-EGF). Apart from juxtacrine effect, proHB-EGF undergoes ectodomain shedding to generate its mature version the soluble HB-EGF (sHB-EGF), which binds to its downstream receptors (such as EGFR) to impose pathophysiological functions with regards to cell proliferation, survival, migration, and differentiation [9,10]. HB-EGF is constitutively expressed in the brain including endothelial cells, glial cells and neurons [9]. Under diseased conditions, such as ischemia or neuroinflammation, the expression of proHB-EGF on the endothelium is increased, which could offer a window for efficient drug delivery into the diseased brain [11,12]. More importantly, no endogenous ligand of proHB-EGF has been identified so far [13], hence no issues in terms of binding competition or blocking of essential nutrients transporters on the BBB. Altogether, these properties make proHB-EGF an applicable RMT target for the delivery of therapeutic molecules across the BBB.

Cross-reacting material 197 (CRM197), a non-toxic derivative of the Diphtheria toxin (DT) [14], is capable of binding proHB-EGF and carrying drugs across the BBB via RMT [13]. While CRM197 represented a promising BBB shuttle molecule, it was found to retain weak toxicity, such as inhibition of protein synthesis, DNA endonucleolytic degradation and depolymerization of cytoskeleton proteins [15–18]. Besides, CRM197 incubation was found to induce a more permeable BBB [19]. Notably, CRM197 can also utilize caveolae pathway to cross the BBB, which is however proHB-EGF binding independent [19–22]. As the caveolae transport mechanism is widely presented in endothelial cells across the body [23], it is concerning whether CRM197 would have off-target effects during the intravenous injection (IV)-based BBB targeting process thereby causing unexpected biological effects.

Here we present a new approach utilizing proHB-EGF-mediated transcytosis. Being among the smallest antigen-binding units ever developed (~15 kDa), the heavy chain variable domain of the heavy-chain-only antibodies (VHHs), also known as nanobodies (Nbs), have gained particular attention over full size antibodies (~150 kDa) in the field of targeted drug delivery due to their lower immunogenicity, better structural stability and deeper tissue penetration [24,25]. Previously, we demonstrated the employment of a VHH for the transcytosis through epithelial barriers by targeting human polymeric immunoglobulin receptor (pIgR) [26]. In this study, we explored the capability of the Nbs to transcytose the BBB by targeting proHB-EGF. Two Nbs named F12 and H7 were isolated, which selectively bound to both proHB-EGF and sHB-EGF. These Nbs were generated by immunization of llamas with the ectodomain of human proHB-EGF and sHB-EGF, followed by phage display selections. We confirmed that both Nbs were able to undergo RMT in the *in-vitro* transwell BBB models comprising of either primary human brain microvascular endothelial cells (hBMECs) or human induced pluripotent stem cell (hiPSC)-derived BMEC-like cells. Our data suggested that these proHB-EGF targeting Nbs could be competent BBB shuttle molecules for the delivery of therapeutics into the brain.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Cell culture

Primary Human Brain Microvascular Endothelial Cells (hBMECs) (ACBRI 376) were purchased from Cell Systems. Cells were maintained in culture flasks coated with 50 µg/ml collagen-IV (C5533, Sigma-Aldrich) and 25 µg/ml fibronectin (F4759, Sigma-Aldrich) in MV-2 medium (C-2212, Promocell) supplemented with 1 × Antibiotic Antimycotic reagent (A5955, Sigma-Aldrich) and in a 5 % CO₂ humidified incubator at 37 °C. Medium was refreshed every two days. Upon reaching confluency around 70 %, cells were detached with 0.025 % trypsin EDTA (#25300054, Thermo Fisher Scientific) and sub-cultured at a ratio between 1:3–1:6 in newly coated flasks. Cells were used for experiments with no more than 9 passages. The primary human

astrocytes (#1800) were purchased from ScienCell. Cells were maintained in culture flasks coated with hESC-qualified Matrigel (#354277, Corning) in a 5 % CO₂ humidified incubator at 37 °C. Astrocyte growth medium (AGM, #1801, ScienCell) supplemented with 1 × Antibiotic Antimycotic reagent was used, which was refreshed every two days. Upon reaching 90 % confluency, the astrocytes were detached with 0.025 % trypsin EDTA and sub-cultured at the density of 5,000 cells/cm² in new coated flasks. The astrocytes were used for experiments with no more than 10 passages. The hiPSCs were generated in the lab from IMR90 fibroblast cell line by episomal plasmid transfection method, as previously reported by others [27]. The hiPSCs were feeder-freely maintained in StemFlex medium (A3349401, Thermo Fisher Scientific) in 6-well plates coated with hESC-qualified Matrigel in a 5 % CO₂ humidified incubator at 37 °C. Medium was refreshed daily. Upon reaching 70 % confluency, cells were washed once with PBS and detached with ReleSR (#05872, STEMCELL) and sub-cultured as colonies at a ratio between 1:10–1:20 in new coated well plate. The hiPSCs were used for experiments with no more than 50 passages. The COS-7 cell line (CRL-1651, ATCC) was maintained in culture flasks in low glucose DMEM (D6046, Sigma-Aldrich) containing 10 % FBS (v/v) and 1 × Antibiotic Antimycotic reagent. The U87 cell line (HTB-14, ATCC) was maintained in culture flasks in low glucose DMEM containing 10 % (v/v) FBS and 1 × Antibiotic Antimycotic reagent. The b.End.3 cell line (CRL-2299, ATCC) was maintained in culture flasks in high glucose DMEM (D6429, Sigma-Aldrich) containing 10 % (v/v) FBS and 1 × Antibiotic Antimycotic reagent. All cell lines were regularly tested for mycoplasma contamination and were all found negative.

2.2. HB-EGF transfection of COS-7 cells

COS-7 cells were seeded in the wells of the 6-well plate. Upon reaching 85 % confluency, cells were transiently transfected with plasmid expressing the full-length clone of human HB-EGF carrying a C-terminal GFP tag (HG10325-ACG, SinoBio) using Lipofectamine 3000 reagent (L3000001, Thermo Fisher Scientific). Two days after transfection, cells showed the most intense membranous GFP signal and were detached with trypsin EDTA and seeded in well plates for experiments.

2.3. Llama immunization

Immunizations of two llamas were performed at Kaneka Eurogentec S.A (Liege, Belgium). Primarily, both animals received 4 injections of a purified protein mixture consisting of 15 µg human pre-proHB-EGF (ectodomain, 20-148aa) (#215635, Abcam) and 15 µg sHB-EGF (64-148aa) (#269156, Abcam) (Fig. 1a) at an interval of 2 weeks. For the final booster injection, 2 weeks after the final injection with purified proteins, two llamas were injected with purified membrane vesicles prepared from 2 × 10⁷ COS-7 cells transiently transfected to express full-length human HB-EGF, following a published method [28].

2.4. Immune response evaluation

To validate the immune response of the llamas towards HB-EGF, sera titers were evaluated via enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA). MaxiSorp 96-well plates (#44240421, Thermo Fisher Scientific) were overnight coated with 50 ng/well of either pre-proHB-EGF (20-148aa) or sHB-EGF (64-148aa) in 50 mM carbonate buffer (pH 9.4) at 4 °C. The following day, the coating solution was removed, and the wells were blocked with 2 % (w/v) bovine serum albumin (BSA) (A2153, Sigma-Aldrich) in PBS for 2 h at room temperature (RT). Serially diluted sera (1–10⁶ times) were added to the coated wells and incubated for 1.5 h at RT, followed by 3 times washing in PBS containing 1 % (w/v) BSA and 1 time washing in PBS alone. The wells were incubated with rabbit anti-VHH antibody (QE19, QVQ) for 2 h at RT, followed by the same washing procedure as mentioned above. The wells were then incubated with donkey anti-rabbit IRDye® 680RD antibody (#926-68073, LI-

Fig. 1. Isolation of proHB-EGF targeting Nbs. (a) Schematic structure of HB-EGF. (b) Titer determination of llama sera collected at indicated days during immunization. (c) Nb binding analysis of five indicated Nbs to sHB-EGF or pre-proHB-EGF. (d) ProHB-EGF targeting Nbs (F12, H7) and negative Nb (R2) conjugated to Alexa Fluor-647 dye were analyzed by SDS-PAGE and tested for binding to sHB-EGF. Alexa Fluor-647 labeled CRM197 was used as a positive control. Graph shows mean \pm standard deviation. (e) COS-7 cells transfected with GFP-labeled full length human HB-EGF were incubated with Alexa Fluor-647 labeled Nbs or commercial anti-proHB-EGF antibody at 4 degree and imaged by confocal microscopy. Scale bars are 50 μ m. Cell nuclei were stained with Hoechst dye.

COR, 1:1000) for 1 h at RT in the dark, followed by the same washing procedure as mentioned above. The wells were finally supplied with fresh PBS and the signal indicating binding was detected using the Odyssey® infrared imaging system at 700 nm. Data was analyzed by GraphPad Prism 9 software.

2.5. Library construction and phage selection

Total mRNA isolated from the peripheral blood lymphocytes (PBLs) of two llamas was transcribed into cDNA, and specific primers were used to amplify the VHH regions, which were ligated into the phagemid vector pUR8100-Myc-His as described previously [29]. Transformation of electrocompetent TG1 cells and co-infection with helper phage resulted in the generation of two libraries named “SNL166 & SNL167”, which had a size of 2.5×10^6 and 1.15×10^7 transformants, respectively. The generated libraries were applied for phage selection on pre-proHB-EGF (20-148aa) and sHB-EGF (64-148aa), respectively. The SNL 166 phage library and the SNL 167 phage library were applied

separately in each two selection rounds on either the pre-proHB-EGF or sHB-EGF ectodomain. The output phages ($4 \times$ test groups) from both libraries were pooled together to be used for the final selection round on the murine b.End.3 cells, given the need to perform possible preclinical evaluation. After the final panning round, the newly infected TG1 cells were plated on agar plates supplemented with 100 μ g/ml kanamycin and grown overnight at 37 $^{\circ}$ C. The screening of the monoclonal phages for their binding to pre-proHB-EGF and/or sHB-EGF ectodomain was evaluated by phage ELISA. Single colonies were picked and grown in $2 \times$ YT broth supplemented with 100 μ g/ml kanamycin and 2 % (w/v) glucose in the U-bottom 96-well plates (#351177, Corning) at 37 $^{\circ}$ C. When OD (optical density) 600 of the cultures reached around 0.5 (equals around 4×10^8 cells/ml), the cultures were infected with equal amount of helper phage. Cultures were grown for 30 min without shaking followed by overnight culture with shaking at 37 $^{\circ}$ C. Five hundred nanogram of pre-proHB-EGF (20-148aa) or sHB-EGF (64-148aa) were coated per well of the MaxiSorp 96-well plates overnight at 4 $^{\circ}$ C. Next day, wells were washed three times with PBS and blocked in

PBS containing 2 % (w/v) skimmed milk for 1 h at RT. Phage cultures in the U-bottom plates were centrifuged at 4,700 rpm for 15 min at 4 °C, and the supernatant was added to the assay plates in blocking buffer. The assay plates were incubated for 2 h at RT on a shaker followed by five washes in PBS. Mouse-anti-M13-HRP (#27–9421-01, GE-Healthcare) was diluted 1:10000 in blocking buffer and incubated in the assay plates for 1 h at RT while shaking. The plates were washed again for five times with PBS. TMB solution (N301, Thermo Fisher Scientific) was added to the wells, and the reaction was stopped with 2 M H₂SO₄. Absorbance was measured at 450 nm with the FLUOstar plate reader (BMG TABTECH).

2.6. Nanobody production and purification

Phagemids extracted from individual TG1 cells that resulted in binding phages during phage ELISA were sent for sequencing. Sequences of selected Nb clones were further synthesized at Twist Bioscience Corporation, with codons optimized for expression in *E. coli*. In addition, the open reading frame includes an N-terminal pelB signal sequence to facilitate the periplasmic secretion, and a C-terminal cysteine followed by a 6 × His-tag. Synthesized Nb genes were cloned into pET-21 (+) expression vectors followed by heat-shock transformation into competent *E. coli* BL-21 Codon Plus (DE3)-RIL cells (Agilent Technologies). Single colonies of transformed bacteria were picked and pre-cultured overnight in LB medium supplemented with 2 % (w/v) glucose, 100 µg/ml ampicillin and 35 µg/ml chloramphenicol. The culture was then upscaled 1:100 in TB medium supplemented with 0.1 % (w/v) glucose and ampicillin. Nb expression was induced upon reaching log phase by adding 1 mM isopropyl β-D-1-thiogalactopyranoside (IPTG) (I6758, Sigma-Aldrich). Following overnight induction at 25 °C and shaking at 400 rpm, the bacteria were harvested by centrifuging at 4,800 g for 20 min at 4 °C. The resulting pellet was resuspended in PBS and went through 3 freeze-thaw cycles at –20 °C. Periplasmic fraction was separated by centrifugation at 10,000 ×g for 20 min at 4 °C, and the supernatant containing soluble His-tagged Nbs was filtered through 0.45 µm filters before loading to Ni-NTA beads (#30230, Qiagen) for purification. The Nbs were eluted, dialyzed in PBS overnight, and stored at –20 °C. The R2 Nb, which was raised against an irrelevant target, the copper containing azo-dye Reactive Red 6 [30,31], was in-house produced and used as a negative control.

For basic characterization, the Nbs were separated by SDS-PAGE under reducing conditions, and the gel was stained by Coomassie blue. Binding affinities of Nbs to pre-proHB-EGF or sHB-EGF was evaluated following the same ELISA procedure as described above for immune response determination. A non-linear regression curve was fitted for “one site-specific binding” using GraphPad Prism 9 software. Binding affinities of the Nbs represented as K_D (ligand concentration that occupies half of the maximum receptor binding sites at equilibrium) were automatically determined.

2.7. Fluorophore conjugation of nanobodies

Three Nbs (F12, H7, R2) were conjugated to Alexa Fluor-647 fluorophore *via* the single cysteine added to the C-terminal of the Nb, as previously described [32]. Before conjugation, the cysteine on the Nb was first reduced with twice the molar concentration of Tris (2-Carboxyethyl) phosphine hydrochloride (TCEP, C4706, Sigma-Aldrich) in borate buffer (250 mM sodium borate, 250 mM NaCl and 1 mM diethylenetriaminepentaacetic acid, pH 8) at 37 °C for 2 h. Protein labelling kit (A20347, Thermo Fisher Scientific) was used for the site-specific conjugation of maleimide-Alexa Fluor-647 to the Nbs. Free dye was removed by 7 K MWCO Zeba Spin desalting columns (#89882, Thermo Fisher Scientific). Degree of conjugation (DOC) was calculated according to manufacturer's instruction. Percentage of free dye in the Nb preparation was determined by SDS-PAGE followed by gel imaging with the ChemiDoc MP imaging system (BioRad) with a 647 nm laser line.

Band intensities were measured using ImageJ software. In addition, CRM197 (D2189, Sigma-Aldrich), which was used as a natural ligand for proHB-EGF, was randomly labeled with NHS-Alexa Fluor-647 on its lysine using protein labelling kit (A20173, Thermo Fisher Scientific) and purified in the same way.

2.8. In-vitro BBB transwell model

Polycarbonate Cell Culture Inserts (#140652, Thermo Fisher Scientific) with a pore size of 0.4 µm and culture area of 1.13 cm² were used. For the co-culture BBB model, basal side of the insert was first coated with 300 µl Matrigel overnight in the incubator with the insert inverted. Primary human astrocytes were harvested, pelleted, resuspended in 300 µl AGM medium, and seeded on the basal side of the coated insert at 150,000 cells/cm². The insert was inverted in the incubator for another night to allow for astrocytes sedimentation. Next day, the endothelial cells were seeded. First, apical side of the insert was coated with 200 µl collagen-IV (50 µg/ml) and fibronectin (25 µg/ml) (diluted in PBS) for 4 h in the incubator with the basal side of the insert submerged in AGM medium. HBMECs were harvested, pelleted, resuspended in 500 µl MV-2 medium, and seeded on the apical side of the coated insert at 220,000 cells/cm². Meanwhile, AGM medium from the basal side of the insert was replaced by 1,200 µl mixture of 50 % AGM and 50 % MV-2 medium. Cells on the insert were cultured for up to 10 days wherein medium was refreshed every two days.

For the mono-culture BBB model, the abovementioned astrocyte seeding part was omitted. For the generation of hiPSC-derived iBBB transwell model, details can be found in the hiPSCs differentiation method section.

2.9. Nanobody cell binding assay

COS-7 cells transfected with full-length human HB-EGF were seeded in 96-well plates at 40,000 cells/cm² and cultured overnight. Alexa Fluor-647 labeled Nbs (F12, H7, R2) were prepared at 1,000 nM in cold assay medium (basal DMEM +0.5 % (v/v) FBS + 25 mM HEPES (#15630080, Thermo Fisher Scientific)). In parallel, commercial proHB-EGF antibody (#66792, Abcam) was prepared at 1:200 in cold assay medium, as positive control. Cell medium was replaced with Nb medium or commercial proHB-EGF antibody medium and the plate was placed on ice for 1 h in the dark to allow for equilibrium Nb binding. Cells were then washed twice with cold assay medium to remove unbound Nbs. Additionally, for cells incubated with the commercial antibody, a fluorescently labeled secondary antibody was needed for detection (refer to the Immunofluorescence microscopy method section). The cells were fixed in 4 % (v/v) paraformaldehyde (PFA) (P6148, Sigma-Aldrich) for 10 min and permeabilization in 0.1 % (v/v) Triton-X100 in PBS for 10 min. Nuclei were stained with Hoechst (#62249, Thermo Fisher Scientific, 1:1000) in PBS for 10 min in the dark. Cells were finally washed three times in PBS and images were acquired by confocal microscopy (Yokogawa).

Nbs binding to the hBMECs was checked on both adherent culture in the well plates and on hBMEC monolayer in the transwell inserts. HBMECs at 40,000 cells/cm² seeding density were grown in collagen-IV and fibronectin coated 96-well plate in MV-2 medium until confluency. Cells were cultured for 8 days before Nb binding assay. For well plate-cultured hBMECs, the method to access Nb binding was identical as described above. For Nb binding in the transwell BBB model, 500 µl Nb medium was given in the inserts, whereas 1,200 µl assay medium was added in the outer wells. After binding, membrane of the inserts was cut off and placed in plate wells prior to fixation. For confocal imaging, the stained insert was inverted and mounted in the well plate. For quantification, 16 random fields per well from 3 wells were taken at 20 × magnification and the images were analyzed using ImageJ software. Acquired Nb signal was then corrected with Alexa Fluor-647 labelling efficiency. Cell binding data was presented as Nb signal normalized to

the number of cell nuclei.

2.10. Barrier integrity assay (BIA)

Dextran-FITC (FD20S, 20 kDa, Sigma-Aldrich) was prepared in basal MV-2 medium at 25,000 nM (equals 0.5 mg/ml). The transwell BBB inserts (prepared as triplicates) were first washed with PBS (with Ca^{2+} / Mg^{2+}) to remove non-adherent cells and residual medium. For BIA, 500 μl dextran medium was added in the inserts (apical side) whereas 1,200 μl basal medium in the outer wells (basal side). The transwell plate was placed in the incubator for 1 h, where at different time points (20, 40, 60 min) 200 μl medium sample from basal side was taken followed by addition of 200 μl fresh medium and gently shaking the plate. For quantitation, 200 μl medium sample was transferred to the assay plate. Dextran-FITC signal was read using a fluorescence plate reader (FP-8350, Jasco) at 490 nm/525 nm (excitation/emission). Serially diluted dextran samples were made to generate the standard curve. Apparent permeability (Papp) coefficient was calculated using the equation:

$$P_{app} = \frac{(dQ/dt)}{(C_0 \times A)}$$

in which dQ/dt is the transport rate (nmol/ml \times min), C_0 is the initial concentration of dextran in the insert (nmol/ml), A is the surface area of the insert (cm^2). Lower Papp indicated better BBB integrity.

For BBB optimization in terms of barrier integrity, the BBB inserts were tested with different endothelial medium including MV (C-22120, Promocell), MV-2 (C-22121, Promocell), EndoGRO (SCME004, Merck) and with different FBS levels in the medium. Co-culture with human astrocytes was tested in comparison to mono-cultured BBB insert. For barrier enhancement, the inserts were treated with serum starvation medium (MV-2 basal medium +0.5 % (v/v) FBS) with or without db-cAMP (1 mM)/forskolin (10 μM) for 2 h in the incubator. BIA was performed to check the effects of the abovementioned actions on BBB integrity.

2.11. Cell viability and BBB disruption assay

hBMECs were exposed to the Nbs and cell viability was determined. Cells were grown in collagen-IV and fibronectin coated 96-well plate in MV-2 medium until confluency. Nbs (F12, H7, R2) prepared at 1,000 nM in 100 μl MV-2 medium were given to the cells and incubated in the incubator for either 3 h to check acute cytotoxicity or 48 h to check long-term cytotoxicity. After Nb incubation, cells were washed three times with cell medium and treated with 100 μl Alamar Blue reagent Resazurin (R7017, Sigma-Aldrich) prepared at 50 μM in MV-2 medium for 3–4 h in the incubator. After Resazurin incubation, supernatant was collected, centrifuged to remove floating cells, and transferred to the assay plate. Fluorescence signal was measured using the fluorescence plate reader at 530 nm/590 nm (excitation/emission).

Barrier disruption by the Nbs was checked in day 8 monoculture transwell BBB model. Confluent hBMECs in the inserts were incubated with 1,000 nM Nbs or 500 nM CRM197 on the apical side for 3 h in the incubator. The insert was washed once with cell medium and followed by the BIA.

2.12. hiPSCs differentiation into BMEC-like cells

Differentiation of hiPSCs into BMEC-like cells followed a published protocol but with minor modifications [33]. Briefly, the hiPSC culture were washed once with PBS and incubated with Accutase (A6964, Sigma-Aldrich) for 10 min in the cell incubator at 37 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ followed by pipetting for less than 10 times to generate homogeneous single cells. Cells were pelleted and resuspended in StemFlex supplemented with 10 μM Y27632 (#72302, STEMCELL) and then seeded in Matrigel pre-coated 6-well plates at the density of 25,000 cells/ cm^2 . For the next

3–4 days, StemFlex medium without Y27632 was refreshed daily to allow cells to expand. When cell confluency reached around 95 %, differentiation was initiated by switching to DeMedium 1 [DMEM/F12 (#11320033, Thermo Fisher Scientific) + 1 \times non-essential amino acids (NEAA, #11140050, Thermo Fisher Scientific) + 0.5 \times GlutaMAX (#35050061, Thermo Fisher Scientific) + 0.1 mM beta-mercaptoethanol (2-ME) (#21985023, Thermo Fisher Scientific) + 6 μM CHIR99021 (SML1064, Sigma-Aldrich)] for 24 h and this day was marked as day 0–1 of differentiation. For day 1–6, DeMedium 2 [DMEM/F12 + 1 \times NEAA + 0.5 \times GlutaMAX + 0.1 mM 2-ME + 1 \times B27 (#17504044, Thermo Fisher Scientific)] was used with daily medium change. On day 6, DeMedium 3 [human endothelial serum free medium (hESFM, #11111044, Thermo Fisher Scientific) + 20 ng/ml FGF-2 (#100-18b, Peprotech) + 10 μM all-trans retinoic acid (#554720, Sigma-Aldrich) + 1 \times B27] was used and medium remained unchanged for 48 h. On day 8, single cells were obtained using Accutase (~20 min) and mechanical pipetting. Cells were pelleted and resuspended in DeMedium 3 and pre-selected at the ratio of 1:1 in 6-well plate pre-coated with 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ collagen-IV and 25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ fibronectin (co-diluted in PBS) for 1 h in the incubator. One hour later, floating cells were removed and the adherent cells were lifted again, pelleted and resuspended in DeMedium 3. To generate the transwell iBBB model, cells were seeded onto Matrigel pre-coated insert (1.13 cm^2 area, 0.4 μm pore size) at density of 1,000,000 cells/ cm^2 . For western blotting (WB), cells were seeded into Matrigel pre-coated well plate at density of 800,000 cells/ cm^2 . The medium was switched to DeMedium 4 (hESFM + 1 \times B27 + 100 μM db-cAMP (D0627, Sigma-Aldrich)) 24 h later. From now on, DeMedium 4 was refreshed every two days. On day 14, cells in the well plates were used for WB. On day 16, which was 7 days after re-plating onto transwell insert, the iBBB model was used for either immunofluorescence microscopy (IFM) or Nb transcytosis assay.

2.13. Nb transcytosis assay

Nb transcytosis assay was done in the hBMEC-based co-culture transwell BBB model on day 8. Before the assay, the BBB inserts (prepared as triplicates) were treated with serum starvation medium plus 10 μM forskolin for 2 h to perform barrier enhancement. Three Alexa Fluor-647 labeled Nbs (F12, H7, R2) were prepared at the concentration of 1,000 nM in serum starvation medium. Meanwhile, 20 kDa FITC-dextran at 10,000 nM was included in the assay medium as an internal control to monitor BBB leakage. For Nb transcytosis assay, 500 μl Nb solutions were added into the inserts (apical side) and 1,200 μl assay medium was added into the outer wells (basal side). The Nb transcytosis assay took 3 h, where at different time points (60, 120, 180 min) a portion of 400 μl medium sample was collected from basal side followed by replenishing 400 μl fresh medium and gently shaking the plate. All samples, if not immediately analyzed, were frozen at -20°C . To detect Nb transcytosis, medium samples were heated at 70 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 10 min with 4 \times SDS-PAGE loading buffer (#1610747, BioRad) followed by loading onto 4–12 % Bis-Tris gel (NW04120BOX, Thermo Fisher Scientific) and ran in MES buffer (NP0002, Thermo Fisher Scientific). In parallel, serially diluted samples of each Nb were made and ran in SDS-PAGE to generate standard curves. The polyacrylamide gel was imaged by ChemiDoc MP imaging system (BioRad) with 647 nm laser line. Band intensities of the Nbs were measured using ImageJ software followed by correction with Alexa Fluor-647 labelling efficiency. To monitor simultaneous BBB leakage during Nb transcytosis, 200 μl spare medium sample was loaded to assay plate and the dextran-FITC signal was measured by Jasco fluorescence plate reader, as described before.

Specifically, for Nb transcytosis on hiPSC-derived iBBB model, hESFM medium was used as assay medium and no barrier enhancement was performed beforehand.

2.14. Immunofluorescence microscopy (IFM)

All IFM steps were carried out at RT unless specified otherwise. Confluent monolayers of either hBMECs or hiPSC-derived BMEC-like cells in the well plates were washed twice in PBS and fixed either in 4 % (w/v) PFA for 10 min or in methanol on ice for 20 min. Cells were then washed three times in PBS and permeabilized in PBS containing 0.1 % (v/v) TritonX-100 (T8787, Sigma-Aldrich) for 10 min. Cells fixed with methanol did not require a permeabilization step, nonetheless. Specifically, no permeabilization was required if BBB surface marker was to be stained. After permeabilization, cells were blocked in PBS containing 2 % BSA for a minimum of 1 h. Cells were incubated with primary antibodies for VE-cadherin (vascular endothelial cadherin, #33168, Abcam, 1:400), Claudin-5 (#4C3C2, Thermo Fisher Scientific, 1:50), ZO-1 (Zonula Occludens Protein 1, #61-7300, Thermo Fisher Scientific, 1:200), Occludin (#33-1500, Thermo Fisher Scientific, 1:50), GLUT-1 (glucose transporter-1, SPM498, Thermo Fisher Scientific, 1:100), P-gp (p-glycoprotein, #235954, Abcam, 1:100), proHB-EGF (membrane-anchored heparin-binding EGF-like growth factor, #66792, Abcam, 1:200), Caveolin-1 (#2910, Abcam, 1:400), Clathrin (MA1-065, Thermo Fisher Scientific, 1:300) in blocking buffer overnight at 4 °C. For IFM of astrocytes in co-cultured transwell BBB model, additional antibodies were used including GFAP (glial fibrillary acidic protein, #76214, Dako, 1:200) and S100 β (S100 calcium-binding protein B, #76198, Dako, 1:400). Next day, cells were washed three times with PBS, incubated with fluorescence labeled secondary antibodies including Goat anti-Rabbit Alexa Fluor-488 (A-11008, Thermo Fisher Scientific, 1:500), Goat anti-Rabbit Alexa Fluor-555 (A-21428, Thermo Fisher Scientific, 1:500), Goat anti-Mouse Alexa Fluor-568 (A-21422, Thermo Fisher Scientific, 1:500) in blocking buffer for 2 h in dark followed by another 10 min incubation with Hoechst in PBS to stain the nuclei. Cells were finally washed three times in PBS and images were acquired by confocal microscopy.

Specifically, for IFM in transwell BBB model, membranes of the insert were first cut off and placed in the wells prior to the IFM procedures. For confocal imaging, the stained membranes were inverted and mounted in the wells. For 3D image reconstruction, images were taken at 60 \times magnification across whole cell layer with 0.2 μ m slicing interval and 3D images were generated using ImageJ software.

2.15. Western blotting (WB)

Confluent monolayers of either hBMECs or hiPSC-derived BMEC-like cells in the 6-well plates or transwell inserts were washed once with ice-cold PBS and lysed on ice for 20 min in RIPA buffer (#89901, Thermo Fisher Scientific) supplemented with Halt Protease and Phosphatase Inhibitor Cocktail (#78441, Thermo Fisher Scientific). Cell lysate was centrifuged at 12,000 g for 20 min at 4 °C. The supernatant was collected, and the protein concentration was determined by Pierce BCA assay kit (#23225, Thermo Fisher Scientific). For SDS-PAGE, a total of 25 μ g protein was heated at 70 °C for 10 min with 4 \times reducing SDS-PAGE loading buffer (NP0009, Thermo Fisher Scientific) followed by loading onto 8–16 % Tris-glycine gel (XP08165BOX, Thermo Fisher Scientific) and ran in Tris-glycine buffer (LC2675, Thermo Fisher Scientific). For WB, protein samples in the polyacrylamide gel were transferred to 0.2 μ m PVDF membrane (#1704156, BioRad) using Trans-Blot Turbo Transfer System (#1704150, BioRad). The membrane was placed in a tray, washed once with double-distilled water (ddH₂O) and then blocked in Tris-Buffered Saline (TBS) containing 3 % BSA (w/v) on an orbital shaker for 2 h at RT. For primary antibody, Rabbit anti-Human β -actin (ab8227, Abcam, 1:2000) and Rabbit anti-Human proHB-EGF (ab185555, Abcam, 1:1000) were diluted in TBST (TBS with Tween20) containing 3 % (w/v) BSA. Membrane was transferred to a 50 ml falcon tube and incubated with antibody mix overnight at 4 °C on a roller. Next day, the membrane was washed 6 times in TBST with 5 min per wash. For second antibody, Goat anti-Rabbit Alexa Fluor-488

(A-11008, Thermo Fisher Scientific, 1:5000) was diluted in TBST containing 5 % (w/v) skim milk. Membrane was incubated with second antibody for 2 h at RT on a roller in dark followed by another 6 times of membrane washing in TBST in the absence of light. The membrane was then imaged by the ChemiDoc MP imaging system (BioRad) using 488 nm laser line and band intensities were analyzed by ImageJ software. Comparisons of protein expression between groups were performed after β -actin normalization.

2.16. Statistical analysis

All data were presented as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). Statistical analysis was performed by student's *t*-test or one way ANOVA method using GraphPad Prism 9 software. For multiple comparisons, either Tukey's multiple comparisons tests or Dunnett's multiple comparisons tests was performed. *P* values <0.05 were considered statistically significant.

3. Results

3.1. Generation of proHB-EGF targeting nanobodies

Two llamas (SNL 166 and SNL 167) were primarily immunized 4 times with a protein mixture of human pre-proHB-EGF (ectodomain, 20-148aa) and sHB-EGF (64-148aa) (Fig. 1a), followed by a booster shot of isolated plasma membrane vesicles from COS-7 cells transiently transfected to express full-length human HB-EGF-GFP. Molecular size of HB-EGF-GFP was analyzed by WB and found to have the expected molecular weight (Fig. S1). Llama sera were collected 28 days later for titer evaluation of the heavy-chain only antibodies. Both llamas were found to have developed a humoral response to the two injected proteins (Fig. 1b). SNL 166 showed a higher immune response towards pre-proHB-EGF compared to SNL 167, whereas the immune response towards the sHB-EGF was equal in both llamas. Notably, as sHB-EGF is generated by ectodomain shedding of the membrane-anchored HB-EGF (proHB-EGF), we hence could deduce that there was also the generation of the heavy-chain-only antibodies against proHB-EGF from the immunized llamas. Total mRNA of the peripheral blood lymphocytes (PBLs) of the llamas was then isolated, transcribed into cDNA, and the VHH regions were inserted into a phagemid vector. After 3 rounds of phage selections, VHHs from 25 resultant clones showed specific binding to HB-EGF (either the pre-proHB-EGF or sHB-EGF or both; data not shown) and were subsequently sequenced. This revealed 12 unique Nb clones. These candidates were grouped into 4 families according to similarities of the complementarity-determining region (CDR) sequences (data not shown). Five Nb candidates coming from different families (named A11, C10, G9, F12, H7) were selected for production. All five Nbs were able to bind to both pre-proHB-EGF and sHB-EGF (Fig. 1c). With comprehensive consideration, 3 Nbs (A11, C10, G9) were excluded due to either a repetitively low production yield or comparably low binding affinity for the target protein. F12 and H7, which belong to the same family and share 98.3 % of the aminoacidic sequence homology, were selected for further study. The sequence homology for F12 and H7 can be found in Fig. S2.

To facilitate the readout of further assays, F12 and H7 were labeled with Alexa Fluor-647 dye. As control Nb, R2, which targets the inorganic compound RR6 [30,31], was in-house produced and labeled as well. All three Nbs were conjugated to maleimide-Alexa Fluor-647 via a C-terminal cysteine on the Nb, as previously described [32]. This conjugation form was found to have no effect on the binding of the Nb to its target [34,35]. All three Nbs achieved a degree of conjugation (DOC) above 90 %, and the free dye percentage was all below 10 % (Fig. 1d). Binding affinity of the Nbs post labelling was evaluated by ELISA again. In addition, CRM197, an innate ligand for proHB-EGF, was labeled with Alexa Fluor-647 and used as a positive control in the binding assay. Both F12 and H7 were found to preserve their binding ability to sHB-EGF

after Alexa Fluor-647 labelling (Fig. 1d). The calculated K_D for Alexa Fluor-647 labeled F12 and H7 was 14.93 nM (95 % CI = 10.55–20.97) and 7.78 nM (95 % CI = 6.38–9.46) respectively, which suggested the binding affinity of H7 to sHB-EGF was two times higher than F12. R2, as a negative control, did not bind to sHB-EGF at all. Notably, as a positive ligand for sHB-EGF, Alexa Fluor-647 labeled CRM197, however, exhibited much reduced binding affinity (>1 mM) than the free form CRM197/DT ever reported (27 nM) [36]. This might be the consequence of labelling Alexa Fluor-647 to random lysine of the CRM197, which resulted in a suboptimal paratope conformation in terms of binding sHB-EGF.

Next, we tested the Nb binding on COS-7 cells. As COS-7 cells do not express HB-EGF, neither the commercial anti-proHB-EGF antibody nor the Nbs showed any binding to cells (Fig. S3). We then transfected the cells to transiently express the full-length clone of human HB-EGF. As the protein was fused to a GFP tag, the distribution of HB-EGF can be clearly visualized in the cells. The cell membrane was found to be outlined with continuous GFP signal (Fig. 1e). Besides, GFP signal was also found in the cytoplasm which might represent newly synthesized protein. We confirmed that both the commercial antibody and the targeting Nbs (F12, H7) specifically colocalized with the membrane GFP signal, indicating binding to proHB-EGF on the cell surface (Fig. 1e). In comparison, the negative control R2 barely showed any binding to the transfected cells (Fig. 1e).

3.2. Nbs have no impact on cell viability nor on BBB integrity

The safety of these proHB-EGF targeting Nbs is a crucial prerequisite for further *in-vivo* applications. Here we investigated the Nb cytotoxicity on the hBMECs. Cells were incubated with 1000 nM Nb for either 3 h or 48 h followed by measurement of metabolic activity of the cells using Alamar Blue reagent. None of these Nbs were found to have acute or long-term impact on cell viability (Fig. 2a). Moreover, we tested whether the incubation of Nbs would cause barrier disruption in a transwell-cultured endothelial layer. The results showed that there was no significant difference as compared to the non-treated control (Fig. 2b). On the other hand, incubation with CRM197 was found to induce substantial BBB leakage (Fig. 2b), which was consistent with earlier studies [19,21,22]. Altogether, we demonstrated that the proHB-EGF targeting Nbs have no obvious cell toxicity or adverse effect on BBB integrity.

3.3. Nbs binding proHB-EGF on hBMECs

We confirmed the presence of proHB-EGF in the hBMEC culture by WB (Fig. 3a). The hCMEC/D3, which is a widely used cell line for BBB

modeling, was used as a positive control for proHB-EGF. Unlike transfected COS-7 cells, on which the bound Nbs were clearly detected with a strong fluorescence signal (Fig. 1e), binding of F12 or H7 to the well plate-cultured hBMECs led to a faint signal similar to that of R2, indicating absence of any specific binding (Fig. 3b).

To check whether proHB-EGF was present on the cell membrane, we compared proHB-EGF staining between live cells and permeabilized cells that were cultured in the well plate. Interestingly, in line with both the proHB-EGF targeting Nbs (F12 and H7) and the commercial anti-proHB-EGF antibody, proHB-EGF was found to be broadly present in the cytoplasm, but rarely any on the cell surface (Fig. 3b). However, on hBMECs cultured in the transwell, proHB-EGF could be detected on the cell membrane (apical side) as dot-like structures by the commercial antibody (Fig. 3c). Consequently, on the transwell cultured hBMECs layer, F12 and H7 demonstrated superior binding over R2 (Fig. 3d). These results suggested that the polarization of hBMECs induced by growing in the transwell triggered redistribution of proHB-EGF from cytoplasm to the apical side of the cell membrane, which might be an intrinsic response of endothelial derived HB-EGF to adapt to polarization.

3.4. Optimization of proHB-EGF expression in the *in-vitro* BBB model

For a competent model to study transcytosis, the presence of RMT targets on the endothelial cell surface should be appropriate in number. We optimized culture conditions to further increase the expression of HB-EGF in the hBMECs, expecting that it proportionally upregulated the amount of proHB-EGF to be displayed on the cell surface. We tested the effect of three commercial endothelial media (MV, MV-2, EndoGFR) on the expression of proHB-EGF in hBMEC culture and found that MV-2 medium was able to induce the highest level of proHB-EGF expression (Fig. 4a). Nevertheless, three media induced comparable barrier integrity in the transwell BBB model (Fig. S4a).

Furthermore, the effect of serum level in the MV-2 medium on the expression of proHB-EGF was investigated. It was found that a serum level of 5 % (v/v), which was originally provided in the MV-2 medium, was necessary to maintain the expression of proHB-EGF compared to low serum level such as 1 % (Fig. 4b). Simultaneously, the effects of serum level on BBB integrity were checked, where the 5 % serum was found to be also critical for maintaining proper BBB integrity (Fig. S4c). Based on these results, the MV-2 medium (containing 5 % serum) was chosen for the culture of hBMECs thereafter.

Cyclic AMP (cAMP) and its analogues (such as forskolin) have regularly been used during the development of *in-vitro* BBB models to induce a tight barrier integrity. However, in the presence of serum, we did not see improved barrier tightness by long-term db-cAMP

Fig. 2. Effects of Nbs on viability and integrity of hBMECs. (a) Cell viability was determined after confluent hBMECs in the well plates were incubated with 1000 nM Nbs for 3 h or 48 h. (b) P_{app} was determined using 20 kDa FITC-dextran after the day 8 hBMECs monolayers growing in the transwell inserts were incubated with 1000 nM Nbs or 500 nM CRM197 for 3 h. All graphs show mean ± SD. Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's multiple comparisons tests; ns indicates no significant differences; * $P < 0.05$.

Fig. 3. Binding of proHB-EGF targeting Nbs on hBMECs. (a) WB quantification of proHB-EGF expression in primary hBMECs and hCMEC/D3 cell line. (b) Well plate cultured hBMECs were incubated with 1000 nM Alexa Fluor-647 conjugated Nbs or commercial anti-proHB-EGF antibody for 1 h and imaged by confocal microscopy. (c) Transwell cultured hBMECs were incubated with commercial anti-proHB-EGF antibody on the apical side for 1 h and imaged by confocal microscopy. Fluorescence image was presented as orthogonal view. (d) The binding of Alexa Fluor-647 conjugated Nbs was tested on the transwell cultured hBMECs monolayer. All scale bars are 50 μ m. All cell nuclei were stained with Hoechst dye. All graphs show mean \pm SD. Statistical analysis was performed using student's *t*-test for panel a and one-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's multiple comparisons tests for panel d; ns indicates no significant differences; **P* < 0.05, ***P* < 0.01.

administration (Fig. S4d). By contrast, this treatment was found to significantly suppress proHB-EGF expression in the hBMECs (Fig. 4b). On the other hand, we found that short-time treatment of serum starvation and cAMP administration [37,38] could significantly increase BBB impermeability (Fig. S4d & e) without substantially changing the expression of proHB-EGF (Fig. 4b).

Glia cells are important for BBB development and maintenance. Co-culture of brain endothelial cells with astrocytes has been widely considered to improve barrier integrity [39–41]. We found that the astrocyte co-culture significantly upregulated proHB-EGF expression in hBMECs (Fig. 4c). In parallel, co-culture with astrocytes also greatly enhanced BBB integrity (Fig. S4e). On the other hand, co-culture with U87 cells, a glioblastoma cell line, slightly decreased proHB-EGF expression in hBMECs (Fig. 4c). Altogether, based on these results, we implemented the optimal cell culture conditions (5 % serum in endothelial medium, astrocyte co-culture, transient treatment of serum

starvation and forskolin) to retain good expression of proHB-EGF in our BBB model as well as providing an optimal barrier impermeability.

3.5. Nb transcytosis in hBMEC-based BBB model

To analyze Nb transcytosis, the co-cultured BBB transwell model consisting of hBMECs and astrocytes, was used as described above. The BBB model was foundationally characterized by IFM on day 6, confirming that confluent brain endothelium was positive for VE-cadherin or ZO-1, and the astrocytes on the backside of the insert were positive for S100 β or GFAP (Fig. 5a). Based on BIA data, the model was used for transcytosis assay on day 8 when the barrier integrity was optimal during a monitoring period of 10 days (Fig. S4b). Before the assay, the BBB model was shortly treated with serum starvation and forskolin stimulation to promote barrier integrity. Alexa Fluor-647 labeled Nbs (F12, H7, R2) were given to the apical side of the BBB and medium

Fig. 4. Analysis of proHB-EGF expression in hBMECs. (a) WB quantification of proHB-EGF expression in hBMECs cultured in three indicated commercial endothelial media. (b) WB quantification of proHB-EGF expression in hBMECs affected by serum level, serum starvation and cAMP/forskolin stimulation. (c) WB quantification of proHB-EGF expression in hBMECs affected by the co-culture of astrocytes or U87 cells. All graphs show mean \pm SD. Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA. For multiple comparisons, Tukey's multiple comparisons tests were performed for panel a and c; Dunnett's multiple comparisons tests were performed for panel b; ns indicates no significant differences; * $P < 0.05$, ** $P < 0.01$, *** $P < 0.001$.

samples from the basal side were collected hourly for three hours. It was shown that both F12 and H7 exhibited significantly enhanced BBB transport, which was approximately two times higher than that of R2 (Fig. 5b & Table 1). Nevertheless, there was no substantial difference between F12 and H7. A total of 2.569 ± 0.108 % of F12 achieved BBB passage in 3 h, whereas it was 2.309 ± 0.099 % for H7 and 1.271 ± 0.051 % for R2 (Table 1). Notably, despite being a negative control, R2 still exhibited considerable cross-cell passage, which could be the result of either paracellular leakage or nonspecific intracellular transport. Roughly, to exclude Nb passage possibly caused by BBB leakage, we included 20 kDa dextran as an internal tracer during Nb transcytosis. Dextran BBB leakage was found to increase over time but was significantly lower than the passage of F12 and H7, whereas it was close to that of R2. This indicated that the passage of R2 could result from paracellular leakage, meanwhile suggesting an additional BBB transport mechanism for F12 and H7 (Fig. 5b).

To further prove the RMT mechanism of F12 and H7, we stained the endothelial barrier with anti-proHB-EGF antibody and examined if there was colocalization between proHB-EGF and the Nbs. Confocal microscopy revealed that proHB-EGF broadly co-localized with F12 and H7, but not with R2 (Fig. 5c). Importantly, by viewing in 3D, the Nb-proHB-EGF complex can be found not only at the apical side of the endothelial barrier but was also found in the cytoplasm and at the basolateral compartment. The widely aligned complex dots are compatible with a basolateral membrane colocalization (Fig. 5d). This provided strong evidence for RMT of the proHB-EGF targeting Nbs.

Clathrin-coated vesicles are broadly involved during RMT of the endothelial cells [3,4]. To explore the possible involvement of clathrin pathway in BBB transcytosis of the proHB-EGF targeting Nbs, we looked for co-localization of clathrin and the Nbs. Taking F12 as an example, we found it co-localized with or appeared in close proximity to clathrin during transcytosis process (Fig. S5). This suggested the possible involvement of clathrin coated pits during the transcytosis of the proHB-EGF targeting Nbs.

3.6. Nb transcytosis in hiPSC-derived iBBB model

Recently, iPSCs have become a powerful tool to derive various cell types and bear great advantages over the use of primary cells, such as easy accessibility and high reproducibility. Differentiation of hiPSCs into induced brain endothelial cells has been reported and the derivative BBB models (termed iBBB model) were intensively explored for the screening of novel BBB penetrating antibodies/nanobodies [42,43]. To provide more evidence for BBB transcytosis, F12 and H7 were also tested on an iBBB model. We differentiated hiPSCs into BMEC-like cells and confirmed their expression and smooth intercellular continuity of a set of brain-enriched tight junctional proteins such as ZO-1, Claudin-5, Occludin, as well as the expression of brain endothelial-specific markers such as GLUT-1 and P-gp (Fig. 6a). Expression of proHB-EGF was confirmed in these cells, the abundance of which was significantly higher than that of hBMECs (Fig. 6a & b).

A simplified iBBB model consisting of a monolayer of BMEC-like cells was generated in the transwell system. Unlike the hBMEC model, the iBBB model demonstrated superior impermeability, which greatly minimized paracellular leakage of the dextran (Fig. 6c & Table 1). Consequently, the endothelial transport of three tested Nbs dropped drastically. Nevertheless, F12 and H7 still demonstrated significantly higher iBBB passage than R2. The highest transport on the iBBB model, which was achieved by F12, reached 0.121 ± 0.003 % in 3 h (Table 1). In comparison, H7 reached 0.079 ± 0.001 % in 3 h. Notably, even though much lower, R2 was also able to cross the iBBB model, as has been seen in the hBMEC model. This indicated again that the endothelial cells were able to transport R2 in a non-specific way. Taken together, with both of our BBB models, we concluded that the F12 and H7 Nbs were able to undergo RMT via targeting proHB-EGF.

4. Discussion

ProHB-EGF is constitutively expressed in the human central nervous system (CNS) including cerebral blood vessel endothelia, neurons, and glial cells, and is strongly upregulated after cerebral ischemia and

Fig. 5. Nb transcytosis in co-cultured hBMECs BBB model. (a) IFM of the day 6 co-cultured BBB model consisting of a monolayer of the hBMECs growing in the insert of the transwell and astrocytes growing on the back of the insert, stained for VE-cadherin and ZO-1, S100 β and GFAP, respectively. (b) Analysis of Nb (1000 nM) transcytosis in day 8 co-cultured BBB model. Medium on the apical side was additionally supplied with 10,000 nM 20 kDa dextran as a barrier leakage indicator. (c) IFM showing co-localization of Nbs and proHB-EGF during transcytosis. White arrow-lines indicate the area for co-localization analysis. (d) 3D IFM showing the proHB-EGF-Nb complex during transcytosis. All cell nuclei were stained with Hoechst dye. All scale bars are 20 μ m. Graph shows mean \pm SD. Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's multiple comparisons tests; ns indicates no significant differences, * P < 0.05, ** P < 0.01, *** P < 0.001, **** P < 0.0001.

reperfusion injury [9,12]. Increased expression of proHB-EGF in the BBB is also observed following neuroinflammation [11]. Therefore, proHB-EGF can be harnessed as an RMT target for shuttling therapeutic molecules into the brain to treat certain brain diseases. Moreover, it is conceivable that single use of a proHB-EGF targeting ligand could provide a dual-targeting strategy [44,45], where, after passing the BBB by proHB-EGF mediated transcytosis it could continue to bind to proHB-EGF enriched targets such as inflamed neural cells [46,47] or brain tumor cells [48,49]. To date, only CRM197 has been explored as a BBB shuttle molecule by targeting proHB-EGF. Thus, the potential of this receptor to facilitate BBB transcytosis remains boundless and merits more investigation. Due to lower immunogenicity, smaller size, and better structural stability, Nbs are favorable for various applications such as *in-vivo* diagnostics, therapy, and drug delivery [24,25,50]. Notably, Nbs have been suggested as a promising tool for the delivery of therapeutic molecules into the CNS [51,52]. Therapeutic molecules that are conjugated to the proHB-EGF targeting molecules can include

chemotherapy drugs, protein-based drugs, and nanoparticles with payload [6,50–55]. In the current study, we derived two Nbs that achieve RMT through the BBB by targeting proHB-EGF. Our results provided promising evidence for further development of these Nbs to serve as a BBB shuttle molecule that carries therapeutic molecules into the brain.

The binding of Alexa Fluor-647 labeled Nbs to SHB-EGF protein revealed a higher binding affinity of H7 than F12, with the K_D of the latter being approximately two times higher. In line with this, H7 showed a slightly better binding on the hBMECs than F12. However, the transcytosis assay has shown an inverse outcome, with F12 exhibiting better transport than H7. The superiority of F12 over H7 was minor in the hBMEC-based BBB model but became significantly more pronounced in the hiPSC-based iBBB model. This might be a consequence of both the presence of a tighter barrier in the iBBB model and the intrinsically better transcytosis potential of F12. The latter can possibly be explained by the favorable Nb binding characteristics of F12, more particularly,

Table 1Detailed Nbs transcytosis data on both BBB models measured at 3 h timepoint. Data were presented as mean \pm SD.

Model	Nb	Nb transport (nmol)	Nb Papp (cm/min)	Nb transport percentage (%)	Dextran Papp (cm/min)	Dextran transport percentage (%)
hBMECs-based co-culture BBB model	F12	$1.28 \times 10^{-2} \pm 5.39 \times 10^{-4}$	$6.31 \times 10^{-5} \pm 2.65 \times 10^{-6}$	2.569 ± 0.108 %	$3.55 \times 10^{-5} \pm 1.96 \times 10^{-6}$	1.443 ± 0.080 %
	H7	$1.15 \times 10^{-2} \pm 4.96 \times 10^{-4}$	$5.67 \times 10^{-5} \pm 2.44 \times 10^{-6}$	2.309 ± 0.099 %	$3.46 \times 10^{-5} \pm 6.38 \times 10^{-6}$	1.407 ± 0.260 %
	R2	$6.35 \times 10^{-3} \pm 2.57 \times 10^{-4}$	$3.12 \times 10^{-5} \pm 1.26 \times 10^{-6}$	1.271 ± 0.051 %	$2.73 \times 10^{-5} \pm 4.24 \times 10^{-6}$	1.110 ± 0.172 %
hiPSC-based monoculture iBBB model	F12	$9.07 \times 10^{-4} \pm 2.56 \times 10^{-5}$	$4.46 \times 10^{-6} \pm 1.26 \times 10^{-7}$	0.121 ± 0.003 %	$3.44 \times 10^{-7} \pm 4.92 \times 10^{-8}$	0.014 ± 0.002 %
	H7	$5.90 \times 10^{-4} \pm 6.74 \times 10^{-6}$	$2.90 \times 10^{-6} \pm 3.31 \times 10^{-6}$	0.079 ± 0.001 %	$3.69 \times 10^{-7} \pm 4.91 \times 10^{-8}$	0.015 ± 0.002 %
	R2	$3.13 \times 10^{-4} \pm 2.80 \times 10^{-5}$	$1.75 \times 10^{-6} \pm 4.38 \times 10^{-7}$	0.048 ± 0.012 %	$3.94 \times 10^{-7} \pm 4.91 \times 10^{-8}$	0.016 ± 0.002 %

Fig. 6. Nb transcytosis in hiPSC-derived iBBB model. (a) IFM of the day 16 iBBB model consisting of a monolayer of hiPSC-derived BMEC-like cells in the transwell, stained for VE-cadherin, ZO-1, Claudin-5, Occludin, GLUT-1, P-gp and proHB-EGF. Cell nuclei were stained with Hoechst dye. Scale bars are 50 μ m. (b) WB quantification of proHB-EGF expression in the hiPSC-derived BMEC-like cells. hBMECs were used as a positive control. (c) Analysis of Nb (1000 nM) transcytosis in the iBBB model. Medium on the apical side was additionally supplied with 10,000 nM 20 kDa dextran as a barrier leakage indicator. All graphs show mean \pm SD. Statistical analysis was performed using student's *t*-test for panel b and one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's multiple comparisons tests for panel c; ns indicates no significant differences; **P* < 0.05, ***P* < 0.01, ****P* < 0.001, *****P* < 0.0001.

the on/off-rates. Cumulative evidence has already suggested that only an appropriate binding affinity to the targeted receptor could result in the best RMT efficacy [56]. As a well-studied case, it was found that the

TfR targeting antibodies/nanobodies with high binding affinity resulted in low transcytosis efficiency [57–60]. Besides, the strong receptor-ligand association could alternatively lead to lysosomal degradation

[57,58,61]. To some extent, this reversed relationship between binding affinity and transcytosis capacity has also been seen for our proHB-EGF targeting Nbs, where H7 did not yield better BBB transcytosis than F12 despite a higher binding affinity. On the other hand, it remains to be determined if F12 has fulfilled its best transcytosis potential. This can be investigated by generating a library of F12 variants differing in the binding strength therefore the correlation between binding affinities and transcytosis efficiencies can be tested comprehensively. For example, by introducing site-directed mutagenesis in general paratope regions (e.g., CDR3) of the Nb, binding affinity of the Nb can be tuned without affecting its binding specificity [60]. Furthermore, Nbs could be made pH sensitive by introducing histidine residues in the CDRs. This strategy was found to increase the antibody-receptor dissociation in the acidified endosome and hence the improved release of shuttle antibodies at the basolateral side of the endothelial cell [61].

Despite being the negative control molecule, we noticed that R2 could also be actively endocytosed/transcytosed by the hBMECs (Fig. S6). Considering that the endothelial cells are equipped with abundant adsorption/uptake/transport mechanisms [62–64], it is not unusual to see low level of unspecific BBB uptake/passage of the negative control materials during both *in-vivo* and *in-vitro* transcytosis experiments [65]. Notably, this could even hold true for the active-targeting molecules being tested. For example, we also found that a number of F12 travelled through the brain endothelial cells without complexing with proHB-EGF (Fig. S7), which suggested nonspecific transport of F12 as well. This could be attributed to the static experimental condition which increases the chance of the endothelial cells to capture and transport these cargos in a receptor-independent way, such as adsorptive-mediated transcytosis (AMT) [63]. In addition, despite that we showed the proHB-EGF targeting Nbs could co-localize with clathrin during BBB transcytosis, it remained a question whether these clathrin pits were encapsulating the Nb-proHB-EGF complexes or not. As clathrin pathway also participates in non-RMT mechanisms including the AMT [63], it requires further research to confirm which transport pathways are involved in the RMT of these Nbs. Necessarily, a tri-localization IFM analysis of the Nb, the proHB-EGF, and the pathway participators such as clathrin or caveolin, could provide more evidence. Besides, specific pathway inhibition assays would also be relevant to comprehensively answer the question [66].

The availability of transcytosis receptors, including expression level and apical surface density, are important parameters to consider when developing a RMT strategy. From both literature and our own study, it was found that various culture conditions can affect the expression and cellular distribution of proHB-EGF [11,67–69]. One interesting observation of the current study was that proHB-EGF showed less display on the endothelial surface when culturing on coated 2D surface (e.g., in well plate), making it inaccessible for the proHB-EGF targeting Nbs. However, in the transwell model, proHB-EGF was broadly detected on the endothelial surface. Cell polarization is an important determinant for endothelial cells to carry out specialized functions such as cell migration, barrier formation, polarized signal transduction, and directional transport or secretion [70–72]. ECM coating, which mimics the basement membrane underlying the endothelium, provides a fundamental environment for *in-vitro* cultured endothelial cells to trigger polarized signaling cascades and the corresponding functions [73,74]. However, the degree of cell polarization induced by mere ECM coating may be insufficient due to the absence of other important environmental resemblances. In comparison, the transwell model, with its apical-to-basolateral chamber design to mimic the polarized nature of the endothelial cells lining blood vessels in the body, allows for a more complete endothelial polarization [75,76]. Thus, in addition to ECM coating, our results suggested that the efficient display of proHB-EGF on the BBB and the enabled transcytosis function of proHB-EGF rely on necessary apical-to-basal polarization. It also indicates that the use of a polarized culture approach, such as the transwell culture system, is important for faithful endothelial binding and transport studies.

Astrocyte co-culture was shown to prevent BBB dedifferentiation by rescuing the downregulation of various functional receptors of the *in-vitro* cultured brain endothelial cells [41,77–79]. In this study, we found that astrocyte co-culture efficiently upregulated the expression of proHB-EGF in the hBMECs. Importantly, it has been stated earlier that astrocyte was a necessary inducer of proHB-EGF expression on the BBB and that the up-regulation of proHB-EGF in the brain endothelial cells under diseased condition also depends on the presence of astrocytes [13]. On the other hand, it was interesting to see that co-culturing with a brain tumor cell line significantly decreased proHB-EGF expression in the hBMECs, the mechanism of which remains to be clarified. Notwithstanding, proHB-EGF currently is not physiologically considered as a “receptor” as there has been no evidence so far of any endogenous ligands recognizing it in the human body. Rather, proHB-EGF/sHB-EGF does serve as a potent ligand in binding to corresponding receptors such as EGFR [10]. The fact that DT toxin utilizes this molecule for cell entry indicates that some non-receptor molecules on the cell surface can also function to transcytose cargos across the endothelial layer. Coincidentally, a recent publication demonstrated for the first time the transcytosis ability of γ -secretase on the BBB, a molecule of which was never anticipated to carry out such function [80].

The imperfect barrier integrity of *in-vitro* cultured hBMEC-based BBB models has been an unsolved issue [81,82]. To exclude paracellular passage of the Nbs due to potential BBB leakage during Nb transcytosis, we included 20 kDa dextran in the model as an internal tracer. The use of different-sized dextran to assess barrier leakage has been a common practice [83]. However, high concentration or long-time incubation of dextran may impact endothelial cell functions in terms of cell adhesion, cell viability, inflammatory response, and barrier permeability [84]. Besides, brain endothelial cells can also actively and unspecifically transport dextran by means of fluid-phase endocytosis (FPE) [85–87], which might contribute to an inaccurate paracellular leakage evaluation during long-time BBB transport studies. Thus, in our experiment, whether the 3 h incubation of dextran in the BBB model will cause a differentiated hBMEC status which subsequently interferes with the Nb transcytosis readout could be further elaborated. Moreover, to exclude specific negative effects on the cells, all groups had been equally treated with dextran. Compared to the hBMEC-based co-culture BBB model, the hiPSC-derived iBBB model yielded superior barrier impermeability, which greatly limited the paracellular leakage for 20 kDa dextran and negative Nb R2. We did not include astrocyte co-culture in the iBBB model as the addition of astrocytes were found to yield a higher barrier impermeability than the monoculture iBBB model (data not shown), which raised the concern that the transcytosed Nbs may fall below the detecting threshold by our current method. On the other hand, the expression of proHB-EGF in the monoculture iBBB model was even higher than that in the co-cultured hBMEC-based BBB model. However, the low transcytosis efficiency of the proHB-EGF targeting Nbs achieved in the iBBB model, as compared to the hBMEC-based BBB model, was noticeable. Notably, most hiPSC-derived brain endothelial cells nowadays should be rather addressed as BMEC-like cells since transcriptomics revealed contamination of epithelial or neuroepithelial transcripts in these cells [88,89]. It was found that neuroepithelial cells also exhibit transient barrier properties and transport functions during early stage of neural development [90]. Yet, there has been no evidence that proHB-EGF enriched in neuroepithelial cells can exert a transcytosis function [91]. Furthermore, the population of generated brain endothelial cells was found to constitute only a small portion [88]. Together, these might explain why the Nb transcytosis resulted from our hiPSC-iBBB model was greatly lower than that from the hBMEC-based co-culture BBB model despite a higher proHB-EGF expression. On the other hand, inconsistent transcytosis results gained from comparable BBB models were not rare. For example, one study found that the hiPSC-iBBB model showed significantly less transcytosis for the TfR targeting antibody than that from an immortalized human cell line-based BBB model, even though the iBBB model expressed much higher TfR [92]. Nonetheless,

despite the immaturity and impurity of hiPSC-derived brain endothelial cells ever reported, the advantages of having high barrier integrity and necessary expression of various functional BBB transporters still make these iBBB models suitable for transport studies [43,93].

Considering the complex endothelial proHB-EGF dynamics we have seen and the shortage of literature looking at how the expression and distribution of proHB-EGF in brain endothelium differ between *in-vitro* and *in-vivo*, it remains challenging that the proHB-EGF-mediated transcytosis data from our transwell-based BBB models can accurately predict for *in-vivo* outcomes [94]. While animal models raise concerns of interspecies differences in the BBB physiology [95–100], the use of more physiologically relevant human BBB models will hold the key to more authentic assessment of these Nbs. For example, the organ-on-a-chip (OOC) models have been used as a novel platform for drug screening in place of animal models [101–103]. It is shown that the BBB/NVU-on-chip models, which integrate 3D culture and microfluidic techniques, can recreate complex *in-vivo* like brain microenvironment [79,104–108]. Importantly, the introduction of medium flow in these models could greatly restrict AMT, which in turn help better revealing the true RMT efficacy of the tested drugs [102,109,110]. We believe the use of such models will be valuable in better predicting the *in-vivo* efficacy of the tested BBB penetrating molecules including our proHB-EGF targeting Nbs.

5. Conclusions

Here we demonstrated the ability of two selected proHB-EGF targeting Nbs to transcytose the brain endothelial barrier *via* RMT. Specific BBB transport of these Nbs was confirmed using both the hBMEC-based BBB model and the hiPSC-derived iBBB model. Evidence for RMT was demonstrated by the transport of proHB-EGF-Nb complex across the polarized endothelial cell layer and the detection of released Nbs at the basolateral side. These proHB-EGF targeting Nbs could be further developed into novel BBB shuttle tools that facilitate brain-targeted therapies.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Boning Qiu: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition. **Sara Pompe:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation. **Katerina T. Xenaki:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation. **Alessia Di Maggio:** Investigation. **Clara Belinchón Moreno:** Investigation. **Paul M.P. van Bergen en Henegouwen:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Enrico Mastrobattista:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Sabrina Oliveira:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Massimiliano Caiazzo:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Author agreement

All authors have seen and approved the final version of the manuscript being submitted. All authors warrant that the article is the authors' original work, hasn't received prior publication and isn't under consideration for publication elsewhere.

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Declaration of competing interest

Major findings of this work have been used for a patent application entitled proHB-EGF VHH (ref: P36735NL00). The author Paul M.P. van Bergen en Henegouwen has shares of QVQ BV. and LinXis BV.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jconrel.2025.113852>.

Data availability

The datasets used and/or analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding authors on reasonable request.

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